

Educating students with autism through ICT during the COVID-19 pandemic

Taxiarchis Vouglanis* and Anna Maria Driga

Net Media Lab IIT NCSR Demokritos, Athens, Greece.

World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2023, 14(03), 264–274

Publication history: Received on 08 May 2023; revised on 20 June 2023; accepted on 22 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2023.14.3.0274>

Abstract

The closure of schools due to the pandemic led to the forced implementation of distance education. For students with autism, this also meant an interruption of the support they were receiving. Parents were asked to provide this support without having the proper training. The interruption of the operation of schools and the transfer of education to the home, also meant a change in the routine of autistic children, an element that caused them an even greater burden.

Keywords: Autism; Pandemic; Students; Education

1. Introduction

In order to limit the spread of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), schools have been closed almost all over the world (67-69). This large-scale closure of schools led to disruptions in children's education, socialization and emotional health (Cachón-Zagalaz et al., 2020; Cost et al., 2021) and increased stress among parents and their caregivers (Calvano et al., 2021; Cameron et al., 2020; Thorell et al., 2021). Although most school-aged children were affected by this pandemic, children with autism are likely to have experienced unique challenges and stressors relative to their neurotypical peers. Studies have found that parents of children with autism reported an increase in behavioral problems such as aggression, hyperactivity, hypersensitivity, and worsening communication skills during the pandemic (Colizzi et al., 2020; Mutluer et al., 2020; Nuñez et al. et al., 2021). In addition, emerging evidence has shown that there have been disruptions to school-based special education, speech and language therapy, physical therapy and occupational therapy services, particularly for younger children, due to the pandemic (White et al., 2021). The use of ICT (70-75) and of literature (76-77) during the COVID-19 pandemic was very useful for children with disabilities and especially autism.

2. Problems in the education of students with autism

Autistic children often struggle in formal educational institutions for many reasons (Goodall, 2018; Hodges et al., 2020). They regularly face sensory challenges within the physical school environment (Jones et al., 2020), complex social expectations and interactions (Mamas et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2019), social isolation and bullying (Aubé et al., 2020; Maiano et al., 2016), a multitude of transitions (Makin et al., 2017; Nuske et al., 2019), and low expectations resulting in part from the prevalence of a deficit-based model of autism (Biklen, 2020).

It should also be noted that there is limited attention to their specific needs, strengths and preferences (Makin et al., 2017), including the care of teachers who do not trust their autistic students and do not know how to include them in the classroom (Roberts & Webster, 2022; Robertson et al., 2003). Such challenges often lead to the educational exclusion of autistic students (Brede et al., 2017; Lilley, 2015), as well as an increased incidence of school refusal (Munkhaugen et al., 2017; Ochi et al., 2020) and mental health complications (Crane et al., 2019). For many autistic children, persistent

* Corresponding author: Taxiarchis Vouglanis

negative experiences of conventional schooling can be profoundly damaging to their sense of self and well-being (Danker et al., 2019).

An important prerequisite is building and maintaining strong relationships of trust between autistic students and their teachers. Autistic students report having better school experiences when they feel greater school connectedness and a sense of belonging (Anderson, 2020; Hodges et al., 2020), especially when they cultivate deep relationships with their teachers (Makin et al., 2017), the who meet their needs with innovative approaches based on their abilities (Hodges et al., 2020). Brede et al. (2017) found that a trusting student-teacher relationship was found to be the strongest predictor of educational re-engagement for a group of autistic students who had been repeatedly excluded from school.

In the classroom context, caring goes beyond the interpersonal pragmatics of a caring personality and entails a space where teachers are invested in meeting the needs of individual children and where children are able to take responsibility for themselves and their own experience. (Wood, 2015). This relational view of education is particularly important for autistic children, given its attention to need fulfillment (Murray, 2002) and valuing autonomy, interdependence, community, equality, and inclusion (Tichnor-Wagner & Allen, 2016; Wood, 2015).

Most relationships between autistic students and their teachers are qualitatively poorer than those of age-matched non-autistic students or students with intellectual disabilities and are often characterized by less closeness and more conflict (Blacher et al., 2014; Caplan et al., 2016; Robertson et al., 2003). From the teachers' point of view, the challenging or problematic behaviors of autistic children increase the conflict in their relationships. Conversely, an autistic child's ability to engage in expected (i.e., non-autistic) social skills predicts a closer teacher-child relationship (Blacher et al., 2014; Caplan et al., 2016). In other words, the more "autistic" a child acts out in the classroom (eg, externalizing stereotypic behaviors), the more the relationship is defined by conflict rather than care.

3. The effects of school closures on children with autism

Long-term school closures and the sudden shift to virtual learning are thought to have had a disproportionate, adverse impact on children with special needs (Bellomo et al., 2020; Lim et al., 2020; Vouglanis, 2020; Vouglanis & Driga, 2022; 2023; White et al., 2021). A characteristic of autism that may have created unique challenges for these children during the pandemic is a preference for sameness and routines (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Insistence on sameness can cause anxiety when changes outside of the "typical" routine are abrupt (Wigham et al., 2015). Indeed, studies have shown that disruptions in routine and insistence on similarity were associated with a number of subsequent outcomes, such as increased behavioral outbursts, generalized anxiety and aggression in children with autism, and increased anxiety in their parents (Baribeau et al., 2021; Bearss et al., 2016; Bull et al., 2015; Kanne & Mazurek, 2011; Reese et al., 2005). In the case of the pandemic, parents have reported increased anxiety in their children with autism spectrum disorder due to the changes it has brought about (Colizzi et al., 2020; Alhuzimi, 2021).

Studies conducted so far present a mixed set of experiences. On the one hand, distance learning took place from home, which can be considered a particularly challenging learning environment for many autistic children especially given the associated stressors associated with COVID-19 (Corbett et al., 2021; Toseeb et al., 2020). Autistic children are expected to have struggled even more than non-autistic children as a result of changing expectations and learning environments, untrained and unprepared parents replacing teachers, absence of regular support, less clear teaching, increased provision of undifferentiated curricula and stressful conditions at home. Many autistic children and young people also have co-occurring mental health problems, particularly anxiety and depression (Lai et al., 2019), which are likely to have worsened during the pandemic for a variety of reasons, including discontinuity of care (Oakley et al., 2021).

In addition, many autistic children receive specialist support at school and benefit from close communication and collaboration between families and schools – which were at risk of being disrupted during the pandemic with the sudden shift to distance education. Strong family-school relationships ensure that parents, teachers, and ideally students themselves, share knowledge and expertise to promote the educational outcomes and social-emotional well-being of autistic children (Azad & Mandell, 2016).

For example, in the qualitative study by Latzer et al. (2021), Israeli parents of autistic children, most of whom attended special education, expressed concerns that they did not have the knowledge or resources to meet their children's developmental needs. In a UK-based survey of 339 families of children with special educational needs, most (81%) of whom were autistic, only 40% of parents reported that the level of support provided to help their children's learning by during the pandemic was sufficient (Toseeb et al., 2020). These families reported wanting specialist professional advice from teachers and other school staff on how to support their children's academic and mental health needs, as

well as educational activities that were specifically tailored to their children's needs and consistent with their support plans .

On the other hand, homeschooling, even under such troubling circumstances, could also present some distinct advantages for autistic students (Reicher, 2020). Home environments, after all, offer less opportunity for the sensory and social overload that often mars the autistic experience in formal education (Aubé et al., 2021; Jones et al., 2020; Maiano et al., 2016; Reicher, 2020), which is a frequently cited reason for parents deciding to homeschool their autistic children (O'Hagan et al., 2021). Consistent with this view, some studies have reported that removing many of the daily pressures typically present in school environments has resulted in some autistic children being more relaxed (Asbury et al., 2021; Rogers et al., 2021) and communicative (Mumbardó -Adam et al., 2021) during the COVID-19 lockdown. Multiple parental attention during this time may also have allowed autistic children to make greater progress in their learning than is possible in a larger classroom environment where they receive less intensive individual support (Latzner et al., 2021).

Parents of autistic children found distance learning challenging and did not feel they received adequate support to meet their children's academic and mental health needs (Latzner et al., 2021; Toseeb et al., 2020). However, some aspects of home schooling have been shown to be beneficial. The investment of time by parents, combined with the calmer, less intense, less sensory, and less scheduled home environment, appeared to contribute to a marked uplift in many children's experiences that parallel those of neurotypical children. For example, Ewing & Vu (2021) analyzing public responses on Twitter during the initial phase of the pandemic revealed that parents often promoted the positive effects of learning from home.

Studies examining teachers' perspectives on distance education during COVID-19 have reported stress caused by sudden changes in their working practices, but also their deep concern for their particularly vulnerable students and their willingness to support them (Gudmundsdottir & Hathaway, 2020), with many suggesting that there will be more frequent and more authentic collaborative relationships in the future (Crane et al., 2021).

The study by Azad et al. (2018) on parent-teacher communication showed that neither parents nor teachers wanted to approach the other for greater involvement as well as both felt frustrated by others' perceived lack of confidence in their own experience. In other words, it is possible that teachers felt that parents were the experts who did not need their input and support, and parents felt powerless to ask for more support and input from teachers (Bubb & Jones, 2020).

It's possible that educators are struggling to cope with the pandemic and/or simply didn't know how best to support autistic children remotely. Given that teachers' level of autism knowledge and understanding is a possible explanation for poorer student outcomes (Anderson, 2020; O'Hagan et al., 2021), it is plausible that teachers may simply not know what tangible steps to make to effectively support their autistic students at a distance (Haspel & Lauderdale-Littin, 2020). They may also have relied heavily on autism stereotypes, wrongly assuming that their autistic students were unable, or unwilling, to connect with their teachers and peers during this time. They may also have assumed, albeit incorrectly, that the lockdown would "suit" autistic students, a narrative that was pervasive in all lockdowns, failing to recognize the unique challenges the pandemic posed to their autistic students and their families (Friedman , 2021).

The sensory stress and overload of the classroom and school can be a source of profound distress for many autistic children (Anderson, 2020; Ashburner et al., 2008), and sensory demands are reported as a significant source of stress for autistic students in the classroom (O ' Hagan et al., 2021). Children were freed from the rigid and strictly enforced time structures of formal schooling, which meant that learning could take place more individually to suit each child and their needs and preferences on a particular day. Consequently, children could choose when they needed breaks, choose how to organize their learning over the course of a day and week, adopt a pace that best suited their learning style and capacity for sustained engagement, and gain autonomy in organizing their day to meet their own changing needs.

4. Conclusions

Finally, it's critical to emphasize how beneficial and productive digital technologies are for the field of education. The use of these technologies, which include mobile devices (82-86), a range of ICT apps (87-99), AI & STEM ROBOTICS (100-114), and games (115-117), facilitates and improves educational processes including evaluation, intervention, and learning. Additionally, the use of ICTs along with theories and models of metacognition, mindfulness, meditation, and the development of emotional intelligence [118-152], along with environmental factors and nutrition [78-81], accelerates and improves educational practices and outcomes, especially for autistic students.

More specifically the COVID-19 pandemic has led to stay-at-home and school closures that have posed significant and unique challenges for families of people with neurodevelopmental disorders. There is limited research on how children on the autism spectrum and their families cope with life crises or major disruptions, and prior to COVID-19, there was no research assessing how individuals on the autism spectrum are affected by pandemics. Pandemics are unique in that they require separation, isolation, and quarantine that result in disruptions to family and social patterns and routines. The unpredictable and uncertain events and changes that have occurred as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic may present specific challenges for children on the autism spectrum, but significant benefits can also arise.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The Authors would like to thank Net Media Lab Mind-Brain R&D Team for their support.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors proclaim no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Alhuzimi, T. (2021). Stress and emotional wellbeing of parents due to change in routine for children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) at home during COVID-19 pandemic in Saudi Arabia. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 108, 103822.
- [2] American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*. Virginia, United States: American Psychiatric Association.
- [3] Anderson, L. (2020). Schooling for pupils with autism spectrum disorder: Parents' perspectives. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 50, 4356-4366.
- [4] Asbury, K., Fox, L., Deniz, E., Code, A., & Toseeb, U. (2021). How is COVID-19 affecting the mental health of children with special educational needs and disabilities and their families?. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 51(5), 1772-1780.
- [5] Ashburner, J., Ziviani, J., & Rodger, S. (2008). Sensory processing and classroom emotional, behavioral, and educational outcomes in children with autism spectrum disorder. *The American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 62(5), 564-573.
- [6] Aubé, B., Follenfant, A., Goudeau, S., & Derguy, C. (2021). Public stigma of autism spectrum disorder at school: Implicit attitudes matter. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 51, 1584-1597.
- [7] Azad, G., & Mandell, D. S. (2016). Concerns of parents and teachers of children with autism in elementary school. *Autism*, 20(4), 435-441.
- [8] Azad, G. F., Marcus, S. C., Sheridan, S. M., & Mandell, D. S. (2018). Partners in school: An innovative parent-teacher consultation model for children with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, 28(4), 460-486.
- [9] Baribeau, D. A., Vigod, S., Pullenayegum, E., Kerns, C. M., Mirenda, P., Smith, I. M., & Szatmari, P. (2021). Co-occurring trajectories of anxiety and insistence on sameness behaviour in autism spectrum disorder. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 218(1), 20-27.
- [10] Bearss, K., Taylor, C. A., Aman, M. G., Whittemore, R., Lecavalier, L., Miller, J., ... & Scahill, L. (2016). Using qualitative methods to guide scale development for anxiety in youth with autism spectrum disorder. *Autism*, 20(6), 663-672.
- [11] Bellomo, T. R., Prasad, S., Munzer, T., & Laventhal, N. (2020). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on children with autism spectrum disorders. *Journal of Pediatric Rehabilitation Medicine*, 13(3), 349-354.
- [12] Biklen, D. (2020). Presuming competence, belonging, and the promise of inclusion: The US experience. *Prospects*, 49, 233-247.
- [13] Blacher, J., Howell, E., Lauderdale-Littin, S., Reed, F. D. D., & Laugeson, E. A. (2014). Autism spectrum disorder and the student teacher relationship: A comparison study with peers with intellectual disability and typical development. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 8(3), 324-333.

- [14] Brede, J., Remington, A., Kenny, L., Warren, K., & Pellicano, E. (2017). Excluded from school: Examining the educational experiences of students on the autism spectrum. *Autism and Developmental Language Impairments*, 2, 1-20.
- [15] Bubb, S., & Jones, M. A. (2020). Learning from the COVID-19 home-schooling experience: Listening to pupils, parents/carers and teachers. *Improving schools*, 23(3), 209-222.
- [16] Bull, L. E., Oliver, C., Callaghan, E., & Woodcock, K. A. (2015). Increased exposure to rigid routines can lead to increased challenging behavior following changes to those routines. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 45, 1569-1578.
- [17] Cachón-Zagalaz, J., Sánchez-Zafra, M., Sanabrias-Moreno, D., González-Valero, G., Lara-Sánchez, A. J., & Zagalaz-Sánchez, M. L. (2020). Systematic review of the literature about the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the lives of school children. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 569348.
- [18] Calvano, C., Engelke, L., Di Bella, J., Kindermann, J., Renneberg, B., & Winter, S. M. (2021). Families in the covid-19 pandemic: Parental stress, parent mental health and the occurrence of adverse childhood experiences—results of a representative survey in germany. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 1-13.
- [19] Cameron, E. E., Joyce, K. M., Delaquis, C. P., Reynolds, K., Protudjer, J. L., & Roos, L. E. (2020). Maternal psychological distress & mental health service use during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of affective disorders*, 276, 765-774.
- [20] Caplan, B., Feldman, M., Eisenhower, A., & Blacher, J. (2016). Student–teacher relationships for young children with autism spectrum disorder: Risk and protective factors. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 46, 3653-3666.
- [21] Colizzi, M., Sironi, E., Antonini, F., Ciceri, M. L., Bovo, C., & Zocante, L. (2020). Psychosocial and behavioral impact of COVID-19 in autism spectrum disorder: An online parent survey. *Brain sciences*, 10(6), 341.
- [22] Corbett, B. A., Muscatello, R. A., Klemencic, M. E., & Schwartzman, J. M. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on stress, anxiety, and coping in youth with and without autism and their parents. *Autism Research*, 14(7), 1496-1511.
- [23] Cost, K. T., Crosbie, J., Anagnostou, E., Birken, C. S., Charach, A., Monga, S., ... & Korczak, D. J. (2021). Mostly worse, occasionally better: impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of Canadian children and adolescents. *European child & adolescent psychiatry*, 1-14.
- [24] Crane, L., Jones, L., Prosser, R., Taghrizi, M., & Pellicano, E. (2019). Parents' views and experiences of talking about autism with their children. *Autism*, 23(8), 1969-1981.
- [25] Crane, L., Adu, F., Arocas, F., Carli, R., Eccles, S., Harris, S., ... & Wright, A. (2021). Vulnerable and forgotten: The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on autism special schools in England. In *Frontiers in Education* (p. 175). Frontiers.
- [26] Danker, J., Strnadová, I., & Cumming, T. M. (2019). "They don't have a good life if we keep thinking that they're doing it on purpose!": Teachers' Perspectives on the Well-Being of Students with Autism. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 49, 2923-2934.
- [27] Ewing, L. A., & Vu, H. Q. (2021). Navigating 'home schooling'during COVID-19: Australian public response on twitter. *Media International Australia*, 178(1), 77-86.
- [28] Friedman, C. (2021). The COVID-19 pandemic and quality of life outcomes of people with intellectual and developmental disabilities. *Disability and Health Journal*, 14(4), 101117.
- [29] Goodall, C. (2018). 'I felt closed in and like I couldn't breathe': A qualitative study exploring the mainstream educational experiences of autistic young people. *Autism & Developmental Language Impairments*, 3, 2396941518804407.
- [30] Gudmundsdottir, G. B., & Hathaway, D. M. (2020). " We always make it work": Teachers' agency in the time of crisis. *Journal of technology and teacher education*, 28(2), 239-250.
- [31] Haspel, M., & Lauderdale-Littin, S. (2020). Autism in the classroom: Teacher self-identified factors impacting success. *DADD Online Journal*, 7(1), 44-55.
- [32] Hodges, A., Joosten, A., Bourke-Taylor, H., & Cordier, R. (2020). School participation: The shared perspectives of parents and educators of primary school students on the autism spectrum. *Research in developmental disabilities*, 97, 103550.

- [33] Jones, E. K., Hanley, M., & Riby, D. M. (2020). Distraction, distress and diversity: Exploring the impact of sensory processing differences on learning and school life for pupils with autism spectrum disorders. *Research in autism spectrum disorders*, 72, 101515.
- [34] Kanne, S. M., & Mazurek, M. O. (2011). Aggression in children and adolescents with ASD: Prevalence and risk factors. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 41, 926-937.
- [35] Lai, M. C., Kasseh, C., Besney, R., Bonato, S., Hull, L., Mandy, W., ... & Ameis, S. H. (2019). Prevalence of co-occurring mental health diagnoses in the autism population: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 6(10), 819-829.
- [36] Latzer I. T., Leitner Y., Karnieli-Miller O. (2021). Core experiences of parents of children with autism during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown. *Autism*, 25(4), 1047-1059.
- [37] Lilley, R. (2015). Trading places: Autism inclusion disorder and school change. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(4), 379-396.
- [38] Lim, T., Tan, M. Y., Aishworiya, R., & Kang, Y. Q. (2020). Autism spectrum disorder and COVID-19: Helping caregivers navigate the pandemic. *Ann Acad Med Singap*, 49(6), 384-386.
- [39] Maiano, C., Normand, C. L., Salvat, M. C., Moullec, G., & Aime, A. (2016). Prevalence of school bullying among youth with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Autism research*, 9(6), 601-615.
- [40] Makin, C., Hill, V., & Pellicano, E. (2017). The primary-to-secondary school transition for children on the autism spectrum: A multi-informant mixed-methods study. *Autism & Developmental Language Impairments*, 2, 2396941516684834.
- [41] Mamas, C., Daly, A. J., Cohen, S. R., & Jones, G. (2021). Social participation of students with autism spectrum disorder in general education settings. *Learning, Culture and Social Interaction*, 28, 100467.
- [42] Mumbardó-Adam, C., Barnet-López, S., & Balboni, G. (2021). How have youth with Autism Spectrum Disorder managed quarantine derived from COVID-19 pandemic? An approach to families perspectives. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 110, 103860.
- [43] Munkhaugen, E. K., Gjevik, E., Pripp, A. H., Sponheim, E., & Diseth, T. H. (2017). School refusal behaviour: Are children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder at a higher risk?. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 41, 31-38.
- [44] Murray, C. (2002). Supportive teacher-student relationships: Promoting the social and emotional health of early adolescents with high incidence disabilities. *Childhood Education*, 78(5), 285-290.
- [45] Mutluer, T., Doenyas, C., & Aslan Genc, H. (2020). Behavioral implications of the Covid-19 process for autism spectrum disorder, and individuals' comprehension of and reactions to the pandemic conditions. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 11, 561882.
- [46] Nuñez, A., Le Roy, C., Coelho-Medeiros, M. E., & López-Espejo, M. (2021). Factors affecting the behavior of children with ASD during the first outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Neurological Sciences*, 42, 1675-1678.
- [47] Nuske, H. J., McGhee Hassrick, E., Bronstein, B., Hauptman, L., Aponte, C., Levato, L., ... & Smith, T. (2019). Broken bridges—new school transitions for students with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review on difficulties and strategies for success. *Autism*, 23(2), 306-325.
- [48] Oakley, B., Tillmann, J., Ruigrok, A. N. V., Baranger, A., Takow, C., Charman, T., ... & Murphy, D. G. M. AIMS-2-Trials ECRAN & the AIMS-2-Trials Consortium (2021). COVID-19 health and social care access for autistic people and individuals with intellectual disability: A European policy review. *British Medical Journal Open*, 11.
- [49] Ochi, M., Kawabe, K., Ochi, S., Miyama, T., Horiuchi, F., & Ueno, S. I. (2020). School refusal and bullying in children with autism spectrum disorder. *Child and adolescent psychiatry and mental health*, 14, 1-7.
- [50] O'Hagan, S., Bond, C., & Hebron, J. (2021). What do we know about home education and autism? A thematic synthesis review. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 80, 101711.
- [51] Reese, R. M., Richman, D. M., Belmont, J. M., & Morse, P. (2005). Functional characteristics of disruptive behavior in developmentally disabled children with and without autism. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 35, 419-428.
- [52] Reicher, D. (2020). Debate: Remote learning during COVID-19 for children with high functioning autism spectrum disorder. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 25(4), 263-264.

- [53] Roberts, J., & Webster, A. (2022). Including students with autism in schools: a whole school approach to improve outcomes for students with autism. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 26(7), 701-718.
- [54] Robertson, K., Chamberlain, B., & Kasari, C. (2003). General education teachers' relationships with included students with autism. *Journal of Autism and developmental disorders*, 33, 123-130.
- [55] Rogers, G., Perez-Olivas, G., Stenfert Kroese, B., Patel, V., Murphy, G., Rose, J., ... & Willner, P. (2021). The experiences of mothers of children and young people with intellectual disabilities during the first COVID-19 lockdown period. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 34(6), 1421-1430.
- [56] Thorell, L. B., Skoglund, C., de la Peña, A. G., Baeyens, D., Fuermaier, A. B. M., Groom, M. J., Mammarella, I. C., van der Oord, S., van den Hoofdakker, B. J., Luman, M., de Miranda, D. M., Siu, A. F. Y., Steinmayr, R., Idrees, I., Soares, L. S., Sörlin, M., Luque, J. L., Moscardino, U. M., Roch, M., . . . Christiansen, H. (2021). Parental experiences of homeschooling during the covid-19 pandemic: Differences between seven european countries and between children with and without mental health conditions. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 1-13.
- [57] Tichnor-Wagner, A., & Allen, D. (2016). Accountable for care: Cultivating caring school communities in urban high schools. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 15(4), 406-447.
- [58] Toseeb U., Asbury K., Code A., Fox L., Deniz E. (2020). Supporting families with children with special educational needs and disabilities during COVID-19. *PsyArXiv*.
- [59] Vouglanis, T. (2020). Teachers attitudes towards the use of ICT in the educational process of people with special educational needs. *International Journal of Educational Innovation*, 2(1), 90-99.
- [60] Vouglanis, T. & Driga, A. (2022). The internet addiction and the impact on the cognitive, psychological and social side of people's personality with disabilities. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 35(1), 93-110.
- [61] Vouglanis, T. & Driga, A. (2022). The positive impact of Internet on the cognitive, psychological and social side of people's personality with disabilities. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 35(1), 29-42.
- [62] Vouglanis, T., & Driga, A. M. (2023). Effects of COVID-19 on people with intellectual disabilities and the ICT's role. *TechHub Journal*, 4, 29-44.
- [63] White, L. C., Law, J. K., Daniels, A. M., Toroney, J., Vernioia, B., Xiao, S., ... & Chung, W. K. (2021). Brief report: Impact of COVID-19 on individuals with ASD and their caregivers: A perspective from the SPARK cohort. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 51(10), 3766-3773.
- [64] Wigham, S., Rodgers, J., South, M., McConachie, H., & Freeston, M. (2015). The interplay between sensory processing abnormalities, intolerance of uncertainty, anxiety and restricted and repetitive behaviours in autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 45, 943-952.
- [65] Williams, E. I., Gleeson, K., & Jones, B. E. (2019). How pupils on the autism spectrum make sense of themselves in the context of their experiences in a mainstream school setting: A qualitative metasynthesis. *Autism*, 23(1), 8-28.
- [66] Wood, R. (2015). To be cared for and to care: Understanding theoretical conceptions of care as a framework for effective inclusion in early childhood education and care. *Child Care in Practice*, 21(3), 256-265.
- [67] Vouglanis, T., & Driga, A. M. (2023). Educating students with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) through ICT during the COVID-19 pandemic. *TechHub Journal*, 6, 40–51.
- [68] Vouglanis, T., & Driga, A. M. (2023). Educating students with dyslexia through ICT during the COVID-19 pandemic. *TechHub Journal*, 5, 20–33
- [69] Vouglanis, T., & Driga, A. M. (2023). Risks, inequalities, and problems of people with Disabilities in the COVID-19 pandemic and the role of ICTs. *TechHub Journal*, 4, 45-58.
- [70] Vouglanis, T., Driga, A. M., & Drigas, A. (2022). Physical and mental exercise to create new congenial neurons, to increase intelligence and the role of ICTs
- [71] Vouglanis, T., Driga, A. M., & Drigas, A. (2022). Charismatic Children: Heredity, Environment and ICTs
- [72] Manola, M., Vouglanis, T., Maniou, F., & Driga, A. M. (2023). The literary hero Sherlock Holmes, his relationship with Asperger syndrome and ICT's role in literacy.
- [73] Manola, M., Vouglanis, T., Maniou, F., & Driga, A. M. (2023). Children's literature as a means of disability awareness and ICT's role

- [74] Vouglanis, T., & Driga, A. M. (2023). The use of ICT for the early detection of dyslexia in education. *TechHub Journal*, 5, 54–67
- [75] Vouglanis, T., & Driga, A. M. (2023). Factors affecting the education of gifted children and the role of digital technologies. *TechHub Journal*, 6, 28–39.
- [76] Manola, M., Maniou, F., Vouglanis, T., & Soldatou, A. (2023). Literary routes in the footsteps of Sherlock Holmes. *SDCT-Journal*, 12(1), 79-85. DOI:0.26341/issn.2241-4010-2023-1a-6
- [77] Manola, M., Vouglanis, T., & Maniou, F. (2022). Contribution of the use of children’s literature in special education. *Open Journal for Anthropological Studies*, 6(2), 21-26.
- [78] Stavridou Th., Driga, A.M., Drigas, A.S., 2021. Blood Markers in Detection of Autism, *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering Science & IT (IJES)* 9(2):79-86. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i2.21283>
- [79] Zavitsanou, A., & Drigas, A. (2021). Nutrition in mental and physical health. *Technium Soc. Sci. J.*, 23, 67. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v23i1.4126>
- [80] Driga, A.M., Drigas, A.S. 2019 “Climate Change 101: How Everyday Activities Contribute to the Ever-Growing Issue”, *International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT*, vol. 7(1), pp. 22-31. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i1.10031>
- [81] Driga, A.M., and Drigas, A.S. 2019 “ADHD in the Early Years: Pre-Natal and Early Causes and Alternative Ways of Dealing.” *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (IJOE)*, vol. 15, no. 13, p. 95., doi:10.3991/ijoe.v15i13.11203
- [82] Stathopoulou, et all 2018, Mobile assessment procedures for mental health and literacy skills in education. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, 12(3), 21-37, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v12i3.8038>
- [83] Kokkalia G, AS Drigas, A Economou 2016 Mobile learning for preschool education. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 10 (4), 57-64 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v10i4.6021>
- [84] Stathopoulou A, Karabatzaki Z, Tsiros D, Katsantoni S, Drigas A, 2019 Mobile apps the educational solution for autistic students in secondary education *Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies* 13 (2), 89-101 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v13i02.9896>
- [85] Drigas A, DE Dede, S Dedes 2020 Mobile and other applications for mental imagery to improve learning disabilities and mental health *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)* 17 (4), 18-23, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.3987533
- [86] Alexopoulou A, Batsou A, Drigas A, 2020 Mobiles and cognition: The associations between mobile technology and cognitive flexibility *ijim* 14(3) 146-15, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v14i03.11233>
- [87] Drigas, A. S., J.Vrettaros, L.Stavrou, D.Kouremenos, 2004. E-learning Environment for Deaf people in the E-Commerce and New Technologies Sector, *WSEAS Transactions on Information Science and Applications*, Issue 5, Volume 1, November
- [88] Drigas, A., Koukianakis, L., Papagerasimou, Y., 2011, Towards an ICT-based psychology: Epsychology, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27:1416–1423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.07.045>
- [89] Papanastasiou, G., Drigas, A., Skianis, C., and Lytras, M. (2020). Brain computer interface based applications for training and rehabilitation of students with neurodevelopmental disorders. A literature review. *Heliyon* 6:e04250. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04250
- [90] Drigas, A. S., John Vrettaros, and Dimitris Kouremenos, 2005. “An e-learning management system for the deaf people,” *AIKED '05: Proceedings of the Fourth WSEAS International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Knowledge Engineering Data Bases*, article number 28.
- [91] Drigas, A., & Papanastasiou, G. (2014). Interactive White Boards in Preschool and Primary Education. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (ijOE)*, 10(4), 46–51. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v10i4.3754>
- [92] Drigas, A. S. and Politi-Georgousi, S. (2019). ICTs as a distinct detection approach for dyslexia screening: A contemporary view. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (ijOE)*, 15(13):46–60. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v15i13.11011>
- [93] Drigas A, Petrova A 2014 ICTs in speech and language therapy *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (ijEP)* 4 (1), 49-54 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v4i1.3280>

- [94] Bravou V, Oikonomidou D, Drigas A, 2022 Applications of Virtual Reality for Autism Inclusion. A review Retos 45, 779-785 <https://doi.org/10.47197/retos.v45i0.92078>
- [95] Chaidi I, Drigas A, 2022 "Parents' views Questionnaire for the education of emotions in Autism Spectrum Disorder" in a Greek context and the role of ICTs Technium Social Sciences Journal 33, 73-9, DOI:10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6878
- [96] Bravou V, Drigas A, 2019 A contemporary view on online and web tools for students with sensory & learning disabilities iJOE 15(12) 97 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v15i12.10833>
- [97] Drigas A, Vrettaros J, Tagoulis A, Kouremenos D, 2010 Teaching a foreign language to deaf people via vodcasting & web 2.0 tools World Summit on Knowledge Society, 514-521 DOI:10.1007/978-3-642-16324-1_60
- [98] Chaidi I, Drigas A, C Karagiannidis 2021 ICT in special education Technium Soc. Sci. J. 23, 187, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v23i1.4277>
- [99] Xanthopoulou M, Kokalia G, Drigas A, 2019, Applications for Children with Autism in Preschool and Primary Education. Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT 7 (2), 4-16, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i2.10335>
- [100] Chaidi E, Kefalis C, Papagerasimou Y, Drigas, 2021, Educational robotics in Primary Education. A case in Greece, Research, Society and Development 10 (9), e17110916371-e17110916371, <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i9.16371>
- [101] Drigas, A.S., Vrettaros, J., Koukianakis, L.G. and Glentzes, J.G. (2005). A Virtual Lab and e-learning system for renewable energy sources. Int. Conf. on Educational Tech.
- [102] Lytra N, Drigas A 2021 STEAM education-metacognition-Specific Learning Disabilities Scientific Electronic Archives 14 (10) <https://doi.org/10.36560/141020211442>
- [103] Mitsea E, Lytra N, A Akrivopoulou, A Drigas 2020 Metacognition, Mindfulness and Robots for Autism Inclusion. Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT 8 (2), 4-20. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i2.14213>
- [104] Stavridis S, D Papageorgiou, Z Doulgeri 2017 Dynamical system based robotic motion generation with obstacle avoidance, IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters 2 (2), 712-718, DOI:10.1109/LRA.2017.2651172
- [105] Kastritsi T, D Papageorgiou, I Sarantopoulos, S Stavridis, Z Doulgeri, 2019 Guaranteed active constraints enforcement on point cloud-approximated regions for surgical applications 2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 8346-8352 DOI:10.1109/ICRA.2019.8793953
- [106] Stavridis S, Z Doulgeri 2018 Bimanual assembly of two parts with relative motion generation and task related optimization 2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems
- [107] DOI:10.1109/IROS.2018.8593928
- [108] Stavridis S, P Falco, Z Doulgeri 2020 Pick-and-place in dynamic environments with a mobile dual-arm robot equipped with distributed distance sensors IEEE-RAS 20th International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids) DOI: 10.1109/HUMANOIDS47582.2021.9555672
- [109] Papageorgiou D, S Stavridis, C Papakonstantinou, Z Doulgeri 2021 Task geometry aware assistance for kinesthetic teaching of redundant robots IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), Prague, Czech Republic, 2021, pp. 7285–7291. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS51168.2021.9636209>
- [110] Kastritsi T, I Sarantopoulos, S Stavridis, D Papageorgiou, Z Doulgeri Manipulation of a Whole Surgical Tool Within Safe Regions Utilizing Barrier Artificial Potentials Mediterranean Conference on Medical and Biological Engineering and Computing DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-31635-8_193
- [111] Stavridis S, D Papageorgiou, L Droukas, Z Doulgeri 2022 Bimanual crop manipulation for human-inspired robotic harvesting <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.06074>
- [112] Stavridis S, Papageorgiou D, Zoe Doulgeri, 2022, Kinesthetic teaching of bi-manual tasks with known relative constraints, Conference: 2022 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS-2022) Kyoto, Japan
- [113] Ntaountaki P, et all 2019 Robotics in Autism Intervention. Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT 7 (4), 4-17, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v7i4.11448>
- [114] Demertzi E, Voukelatos N, Papagerasimou Y, Drigas A, 2018 Online learning facilities to support coding and robotics courses for youth International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (ijEP) 8 (3), 69-80, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v8i3.8044>

- [115] Drigas A, Kouremenos S, Vrettos S, Vrettaros J, Kouremenos S, 2004 An expert system for job matching of the unemployed Expert Systems with Applications 26 (2), 217-224 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174\(03\)00136-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0957-4174(03)00136-2)
- [116] Chaidi I, Drigas A 2022 Digital games & special education Technium Social Sciences Journal 34, 214-236 <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v34i1.7054>
- [117] Doulou A, Drigas A 2022 Electronic, VR & Augmented Reality Games for Intervention in ADHD Technium Social Sciences Journal, 28, 159. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5728>
- [118] Kefalis C, Kontostavrou EZ, Drigas A, 2020 The Effects of Video Games in Memory and Attention. Int. J. Eng. Pedagog. 10 (1), 51-61, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v10i1.11290>
- [119] Drigas, A., & Mitsea, E. (2020). The 8 Pillars of Metacognition. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET), 15(21), 162-178. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i21.14907>
- [120] Drigas, A. S., and M. Pappas, 2017. "The Consciousness-Intelligence-Knowledge Pyramid: An 8x8 Layer Model," International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (IJES), vol. 5, no.3, pp 14-25, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v5i3.7680>
- [121] Drigas A, Karyotaki M (2017) Attentional control and other executive functions. Int J Emerg Technol Learn iJET 12(03):219–233 <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v12i03.6587>
- [122] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2014. Learning Tools and Application for Cognitive Improvement. International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy, 4(3): 71-77. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v4i3.3665>
- [123] Drigas, A., & Mitsea, E. (2021). 8 Pillars X 8 Layers Model of Metacognition: Educational Strategies, Exercises & Trainings. International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering, 17(8). <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v17i08.23563>
- [124] Drigas A., Papoutsis C. (2020). The Need for Emotional Intelligence Training Education in Critical and Stressful Situations: The Case of COVID-19. Int. J. Recent Contrib. Eng. Sci. IT 8(3), 20–35. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i3.17235>
- [125] Kokkalia, G., Drigas, A. Economou, A., & Roussos, P. (2019). School readiness from kindergarten to primary school. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning, 14(11), 4-18. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i11.10090>
- [126] Papoutsis, C. and Drigas, A. (2017) Empathy and Mobile Applications. International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies 11(3). 57. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v11i3.6385>
- [127] Angelopoulou, E. Drigas, A. (2021). Working Memory, Attention and their Relationship: A theoretical Overview. Research. Society and Development, 10(5), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v10i5.15288>
- [128] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2020 A metacognition based 8 pillars mindfulness model and training strategies. International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT 8(4), 4-17. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i4.17419>
- [129] Papoutsis C, Drigas A, C Skianis 2021 Virtual and augmented reality for developing emotional intelligence skills Int. J. Recent Contrib. Eng. Sci. IT (IJES) 9 (3), 35-53. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i3.23939>
- [130] Kapsi S, Katsantoni S, Drigas A 2020 The Role of Sleep and Impact on Brain and Learning. Int. J. Recent Contributions Eng. Sci. IT 8 (3), 59-68. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v8i3.17099>
- [131] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C 2021 The Role of Clinical Hypnosis & VR in Special Education International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering Science & IT (IJES) 9(4), 4-18. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i4.26147>
- [132] V Galitskaya, A Drigas 2021 The importance of working memory in children with Dyscalculia and Geometria Scientific Electronic Archives 14 (10) <https://doi.org/10.36560/141020211449>
- [133] Chaidi I, Drigas A 2020 Parents' Involvement in the Education of their Children with Autism: Related Research and its Results International Journal Of Emerging Technologies In Learning (Ijet) 15 (14), 194-203. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i14.12509>
- [134] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2021 Neuro-Linguistic Programming & VR via the 8 Pillars of Metacognition X 8 Layers of Consciousness X 8 Intelligences Technium Soc. Sci. J. 26(1), 159–176. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v26i1.5273>

- [135] Drigas A, Mitsea E 2022 Conscious Breathing: a Powerful Tool for Physical & Neuropsychological Regulation. The role of Mobile Apps Technium Social Sciences Journal 28, 135-158. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5922>
- [136] Drigas A, Mitsea E, C Skianis 2022 Clinical Hypnosis & VR, Subconscious Restructuring-Brain Rewiring & the Entanglement with the 8 Pillars of Metacognition X 8 Layers of Consciousness X 8 Intelligences. International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering (IJOE) 18 (1), 78-95. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v18i01.26859>
- [137] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2019 Attention and its Role: Theories and Models. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning 14 (12), 169-182, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i12.10185>
- [138] Drigas A, Karyotaki M 2019 Executive Functioning and Problem Solving: A Bidirectional Relation. International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (IJEP) 9 (3) <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v9i3.10186>
- [139] Bamicha V, Drigas A 2022 ToM & ASD: The interconnection of Theory of Mind with the social-emotional, cognitive development of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. The use of ICTs as an alternative form of intervention in ASD Technium Social Sciences Journal 33, 42-72, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6845>
- [140] Drigas A, Mitsea E, C Skianis 2022 Neuro-Linguistic Programming, Positive Psychology & VR in Special Education. Scientific Electronic Archives 15 (1) <https://doi.org/10.36560/15120221497>
- [141] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C. 2022 Virtual Reality and Metacognition Training Techniques for Learning Disabilities SUSTAINABILITY 14(16), 10170, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141610170>
- [142] Drigas A., Sideraki A. 2021 Emotional Intelligence in Autism Technium Soc. Sci. J. 26, 80, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v26i1.5178>
- [143] Drigas A, Mitsea E, Skianis C.. 2022 Subliminal Training Techniques for Cognitive, Emotional and Behavioural Balance. The role of Emerging Technologies Technium Social Sciences Journal 33, 164-186, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v33i1.6881>
- [144] Bakola L, Drigas A, 2020 Technological development process of emotional Intelligence as a therapeutic recovery implement in children with ADHD and ASD comorbidity. . International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering, 16(3), 75-85, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v16i03.12877>
- [145] Bamicha V, Drigas A, 2022 The Evolutionary Course of Theory of Mind - Factors that facilitate or inhibit its operation & the role of ICTs Technium Social Sciences Journal 30, 138-158, DOI:10.47577/tssj.v30i1.6220
- [146] Karyotaki M, Bakola L, Drigas A, Skianis C, 2022 Women's Leadership via Digital Technology and Entrepreneurship in business and society Technium Social Sciences Journal. 28(1), 246–252. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v28i1.5907>
- [147] Drigas A, Bakola L, 2021The 8x8 Layer Model Consciousness-Intelligence-Knowledge Pyramid, and the Platonic Perspectives International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (ijES) 9(2) 57-72, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i2.22497>
- [148] Drigas A, Karyotaki M, 2016 Online and Other ICT-based Training Tools for Problem-solving Skills. International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning 11 (6) <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v11i06.5340>
- [149] Mitsea E, Drigas A., Skianis C, 2022 Breathing, Attention & Consciousness in Sync: The role of Breathing Training, Metacognition & Virtual Reality Technium Social Sciences Journal 29, 79-97, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v29i1.6145>
- [150] Mitsea E, Drigas A, Skianis C, 2022 ICTs and Speed Learning in Special Education: High-Consciousness Training Strategies for High-Capacity Learners through Metacognition Lens Technium Soc. Sci. J. 27, 230, <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v27i1.5599>
- [151] Drigas A, Karyotaki M, Skianis C, 2017 Success: A 9 layered-based model of giftedness International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT 5(4) 4-18, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v5i4.7725>
- [152] Drigas A, Papoutsi C, 2021,Nine Layer Pyramid Model Questionnaire for Emotional Intelligence, International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering 17 (7), <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v17i07.22765>
- [153] Drigas A, Papoutsi C, Skianis, 2021, Metacognitive and Metaemotional Training Strategies through the Nine-layer Pyramid Model of Emotional Intelligence, International Journal of Recent Contributions from Engineering, Science & IT (ijES) 9.4 58-76, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijes.v9i4.26189>